

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

Welcome to the fourth regular issue in 2019 which presents 6 novel and very relevant research papers from various topics in computer science. The presentation of high quality papers continues a collaborative effort which resulted in a continuously improving impact factor. As of 2018, we are very happy to report another improvement of the '5 Year Impact Factor' which is now 0.885. Allow me to emphasize that this would not be possible without the valuable work and feedback of the editorial board and the financial support of the J.UCS consortium. We are continuously looking for experienced and motivated experts to extend our editorial board: so if you are a tenured Associate Professor or above with a good publication record, please do apply for a membership in our editorial board. Please get also in touch with me if your university is interested in joining the consortium and further support the journal, in particular institutions from North and South America might further complement our team.

In this regular issue, I am very glad to introduce 6 high quality papers from authors of 6 different countries and 4 continents.

Namik Delilovic and Hermann Maurer from Austria discuss a mechanism to understand and mitigate mistakes and missing information of websites beyond FAQs and Web administration contacts. Sonia Estévez, M.Emilia Cambroner, Yolanda García-Ruiz and Luis Llana report on their systematic research on mobile applications for people with Parkinson's disease. In a collaborative work between the Philippines, Spain and USA, RJ Macasaet, Manuel Noguera, María Luisa Rodríguez, José Luis Garrido, Sam Supakkul, and Lawrence Chung propose in their work the use of Micro-business Requirements Patterns (mBRPs) for micro-businesses in remote communities. In a collaborative research between Germany and Spain, Robin Mueller-Bady, Martin Kappes, Inmaculada Medina-Bulo and Francisco Palomo-Lozano report about their findings of the applicability of heuristic methods for an automated and reactive optimization of network infrastructures in highly-dynamic communication networks. Diego Pessoa, Ana Carolina Salgado and Bernadette Farias Lóscio from Brazil discuss their findings of improved ontology matching using application requirements for segmenting ontologies.

Giani Petri, Christiane Gresse von Wangenheim, Jean Carlo Rossa Hauck and Adriano Ferreti Borgatto from Brazil report their experimental study about the effectiveness of games in software project management.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor
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